

**MATERIÁLY
XV MEZINÁRODNÍ VĚDECKO - PRAKTICKÁ
KONFERENCE**

ZPRÁVY VĚDECKÉ IDEJE -2019

22 - 30 října 2019 r.

Volume 9

Praha
Publishing House «Education and Science»
2019

Vydáno Publishing House «Education and Science»,
Frýdlanská 15/1314, Praha 8
Spolu s DSP SHID, Berdianskaja 61 B, Dnepropetrovsk

Materiály XV Mezinárodní vědecko - praktická konference «Zprávy vědecké ideje -2019», Volume 9 : Praha. Publishing House «Education and Science» -
70 s.

Šéfredaktor: Prof. JUDr. Zdeněk Černák

Náměstek hlavního redaktora: Mgr. Alena Pelicánová

Zodpovědný za vydání: Mgr. Jana Štefko

Manažer: Mgr. Helena Žáková

Technický pracovník: Bc. Kateřina Zahradníková

**Materiály XV Mezinárodní vědecko - praktická konference ,
Zprávy vědecké ideje -2019**

Pro studentů, aspirantů a vědeckých pracovníků

Cena 50 Kč

ISBN 978-966-8736-05-6

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FINDINGS IN TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT PATHOLOGY AT CHILDREN

¹Olimov S.Sh., ¹Gafforov S.A., ²Saidov A.A., ²Badriddinov B.B.

¹ Tashkent institute of postgraduate medical education

²Bukhara state Medical Institute

It is known, the etiologies and pathogenesis are poorly understood, temporomandibular joint (TMJ) diseases are difficult to diagnose and manage. Definitive and rational diagnoses or treatments can only be achieved through a comprehensive understanding of the etiologies, predisposing factors, and pathogenesis of TMJ diseases. While much work remains to be done in this field, novel findings in biomedicine and developments in imaging and computer technologies are beginning to provide us with a vision of future innovations in the diagnostics and therapeutics of TMJ disorders [Sidebottom AJ., 2013; Wadhwa S, Kapila S., 2008; Wei F., 2013]. Despite of it, a child's difficulty in verbalizing the precise location and nature of facial pain and jaw dysfunction often results in a nondefinitive history, increasing the importance of the dentist's awareness of the early signs and symptoms of TMJ disorders. A focused examination of the masticatory musculature, the temporomandibular joints, and associated capsular and ligamentous structures can reveal if a patient's symptoms are TMJ disorders in origin [Dergin G, Aktop S., 2014; Howard J., 2013; Minghelli B., 2014; Sojka A., et al., 2018; Pizolato R.A., et al., 2013]. In this case the study of techniques identifications of TMJ diseases is a crucial in treatment of medical care.

OBJECTIVE: to study features of some connective tissue markers in development of TMJ pathology at children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: research has been based on medical examination results of 65 children in aged 6 to 15 years with TMJ pathology. Patients' examination was carried out according to scheme, including clinical methods, morphometric methods, biometric study, x-ray methods, dental computed tomography

and serum C-RP concentration which was determined by enzyme-linked immunoassay.

RESULTS: systemic metabolism of connective tissue at patients with dysplasia is characterized by release of glycoproteins, a decrease in sulfated glycosaminoglycan. Beyond, they also is determined rheological properties of blood, which serves as an explanation for occurrence of typical disorders of hemostasis in DAA, affecting thrombophilia caused by systemic inflammatory response, which explained predominance of degradation of glycosaminoglycan on their synthesis.

CONCLUSIONS: as a result of the obtained data, it was revealed that at children with temporomandibular joint disease were a significant increase in glycosaminoglycan level in serum when compared with a group of healthy children. Such study results are likely to help to customize and enhance the quality of care we provide to patients with TMJ disorders. An accurate differential diagnosis enables timely referral to appropriate health care providers and minimizes the use of diagnostic imaging.